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Reflections of the Isis-Osiris Relationship on Cleopatra and Antony in William Shakespeare's *Antony and Cleopatra*

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Abstract:

Influences of the relationship between Isis and Osiris are perceived in the portrayals of Cleopatra and Antony, through the subtle hints provided by William Shakespeare in his play *Antony and Cleopatra*. This paper compares Cleopatra with Isis, and Antony with Osiris, by drawing references to the ancient Egyptian perceptions of living entities, fruits, and wine. The subtle indications given in the text, in the speeches provided to Cleopatra and Antony, provide intriguing instances of ancient Egyptian understanding of the climate, environment, and gender. Applying these findings, the paper argues that Shakespeare has left his valuable insights regarding ancient Egyptian mythical attributes.

Keywords: Isis, Osiris, the Nile, Nature, gender.

Introduction

William Shakespeare wrote *Antony and Cleopatra* more than two centuries before professional Egyptological studies on myths concerning Isis and Osiris began, specifically through iconographic studies and textual translations of hieroglyphic texts from ancient Egyptian

Reflections of the Isis-Osiris Relationship on Cleopatra and Antony in William Shakespeare's *Antony and Cleopatra* tombs, temples, and papyri.¹ A close reading of Shakespeare's *Antony and Cleopatra* reveals elements, living entities, and fruits associated with Osiris and Isis. Antony's speeches and Cleopatra's speeches establish possible associations between them and Osiris and Isis, respectively, and project influences of the mythical relationship between Osiris and Isis.² This article engages in a "mythopoeic" and landscape-specific reading of the play. It refers to the play's inclusion of elements and living entities in (ancient) Egypt, and discusses that these elements are portrayed in opposition to (ancient) Rome. The article explores how the ancient Egyptian ecosystem influences the consciousnesses of the male/masculine and the female/feminine. From Stacy Schiff's biography of "Cleopatra VII Thea Philopator," titled *Cleopatra: A Life*, it can be noted that Cleopatra VII presented herself as Isis to the "Alexandrian" subjects and as a lone mother and Queen in her own right (Schiff 135–136, 1–9, 261–302; see Ray, "Cleopatra VII Philopator's Final Moments" 126–137; see also Ray, "Ancient Egyptian Art and Architecture in *Asterix and Cleopatra* and *Asterix and Obelix*" 3–11).³ With this context in mind, it becomes clearer how Shakespeare's version of Cleopatra VII likewise controls the characters around her with her emotional metamorphoses, assertions, manipulations, and escapades.

Isis and Cleopatra

In Shakespeare's play, Cleopatra's focus on naval power (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 3.7.1–75) and the constitution of gender ambience on her royal barge (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.2.200–230) can be interpreted as having been drawn from mythical references to Isis's connection with the Egyptian solar boat (see Pinch 151, 149–151).⁴ The barge scene, in which Cleopatra sails to meet Antony, offers a study of contrasts: the metallic lustre of the barge blends with the fluidic, aural and olfactory sensation emitting from it; heat and golden

essence surround Cleopatra's barge, which is reminiscent of Isis's connection with the solar boat (Pinch 151, 149–151; see also Ray, "Teaching English Literary Texts with Approaches to Visual Arts" 20–22, 25–27).⁵ Enobarbus is awed by the sun-like brilliance of Cleopatra's barge, even if the barge, with its female and boyish ambience and the sensual delights, contrasts with the masculine weight and strength of Roman warships (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.2.200–230; see also Ray, "Teaching English Literary Texts," 20–22, 25–27). Attending women, "dimpled boys," and strong male rowers place Shakespeare's Cleopatra in the middle of various projections of masculinity and femininity (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.2.200–230).⁶ For Enobarbus, the assembly is predominantly feminine and distracting, aptly aimed for the enticement of Mark Antony (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.2.200–230; see Ray, "William Shakespeare's *Antony and Cleopatra*" 00:49:29–00:50:55, 00:00:00–01:27:24, slide no. 19; see also Ray, "Teaching English Literary Texts" 20–22, 25–27).

In Shakespeare's text, from the Roman viewpoint, their Egyptian adversaries were led by "maids" and a "eunuch" (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 3.7.10–15, 3.7.1–75). Cleopatra projects her leadership in a maritime battle, a quality which typically carries masculine prerogative in the Roman perspective. Cleopatra breaks down the expectations of gender, presenting herself in a masculine manner (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 3.7.15–20, 3.7.1–75). Cleopatra VII's Alexandria was enriched with maritime trade and communication (Tyldesley 115, 109–139). Joyce Tyldesley observes that the "Hellenistic" world of Alexandria provided two important epithets to Isis, expanding her native Egyptian cult beyond Egypt: medical facilities were provided in the temples for "Isis Medica" where patients visited, and ships and sailors departing and arriving at Alexandria's harbor prayed to "Isis Pelagia" for security in marine travel (Tyldesley 115, 109–139). Thus, Cleopatra VII's self-stationed, deified

office was strengthened by the Isis-cult, which in turn was empowered by Alexandria's importance in connection with the Mediterranean Sea.

If Isis had played strategies in the presence of the gods, as described by Geraldine Harris (24–25, 36–47), Shakespeare's Cleopatra assumes the role of commander behind the male Egyptian navy (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 3.7.49, 3.7.40–50, 3.7.1–75). Tyldesley notes that Isis's protection was required by sailors (Tyldesley 115, 109–139). George Hart informs that the ancient Egyptians believed that Isis's cunningness made her surpass “a million gods” (quoted in Hart 82; Hart 82, 79–83; see also Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.2.150–160). A fight on the sea requires calculation, movement, strategy, and an understanding of the air and water. Cleopatra resembles Isis in this context, bringing together male resolution and female subtlety, thereby mixing the two genders. In terms of fluidic, shifting character, Cleopatra becomes an aquatic manifestation; Shakespeare in *Antony and Cleopatra* refers to moisture and earth to project Cleopatra's moods (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.2.150–160). Cleopatra's emotional outbursts are noted as extreme by Enobarbus, who comments that Cleopatra's “sighs and tears” manifest as “storms and tempests” (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.2.150–160). The eyes of a woman or a Queen or a goddess connote energy and power; the Sun's “Eye” (personified as a goddess) destroys with fire, as Aude Gros de Beler observes (Gros de Beler 38–39, 86, 105) while the eyes of Isis enrich the land with water, as Terje Oestigaard notes (Oestigaard 86–88, 72–99). Oestigaard observes that if Isis's eyes cause the flood (Oestigaard 86–88, 72–99), Osiris's body contributes to the flood through his “exudations” (Oestigaard 79–80, 72–99).

It is in the Nile that the phallus of Osiris was lost, consumed by a fish, according to mythology, as Gros de Beler notes (Gros de Beler 74–75). Walid Shaikh Al Arab and Ehab Y.

Ali also note that the fish-goddess Hatmehyt shared an Isis-trait, since Hatmehyt also played a vital role in locating Osiris's "members" in the Nile's waters (Shaikh Al Arab and Ali 126, 121–131). Osiris became a "brother" figure to Hatmehyt (Shaikh Al Arab and Ali 126, 121–131) just as Osiris was a brother to Isis (Wilkinson 118–123, 146–149). The capture of Antony's phallic potential is perceived in Shakespeare's play. While drawing an association between Antony and Osiris, Osiris's lost phallus, which Isis (and in extension, Hatmehyt) sought, can be recalled (Gros de Beler 74–75; Shaikh Al Arab and Ali, "Relationship between Isis and Hatmehyt," 126, 121–131). The fish imagery is indeed significant in *Antony and Cleopatra*, particularly when Cleopatra playfully draws an analogy between Antony and fish (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.5.5–15). Through the representation of Antony as a fish (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.5.5–15), and the mythic consuming of Osiris's phallus by the fish (Pinch 79–80), Cleopatra's preference for fishing is replete with sensual mirth and playful mastery over the phallic potential; she aims to catch fishes with her "hook" and "think" of each captured fish "as an Antony" (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.5.5–15).

Eleanor L. Harris notes that the ancient Egyptians also referred to the fish as a "phallic symbol" (Harris, *Ancient Egyptian Magic* 187–188). In ancient Egyptian art, fishing, watching, gazing in a semi-aquatic environment seemed to have conveyed "heteronormative" desire; Gay Robins observes that in the mastaba/tomb reliefs and paintings, when wives watch their husbands in the acts of fishing amid papyrus or in marshes, erotic undertones are hinted (Robins 187–190). The historic Cleopatra VII watching Antony *fishing* constituted a moment of playful activity; if Robins's observation is applied, Shakespeare's Cleopatra *fishing* Antony herself implies her control of Antony's sexual potency (Robins 187–190; see Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.5.9–15). The readers may read Shakespeare's fishing reference like an ancient

Egyptian believer/reader, who would have perceived the Isis-Osiris relationship in this context concerning Osiris's emasculation and Isis's search for Osiris's phallus, implying her control over his sexual capacity and performance (Viaud 16–20).

The watery turbulence involves elemental variety and shapes the life forms within and around the waters. The Egyptians incorporated crocodile in the myths concerning Isis's companionship with Osiris, following his assassination. The presence and absence of the phallus remained integral for the constitution of Osiris's masculinity and integrity, and Cleopatra's control over Antony's phallic agency resembles Isis's provision of the phallus to Osiris (see Simpson 69, 65–79). In one mythic account noted by Isidora, Sobek's tongue was separated by Isis as a punishment since the phallus of Osiris was eaten by Sobek; in her serpentine form Cleopatra desires the phallic agency of Antony, just as Sobek consumes the phallus of Osiris (Isidora, "Goddess Isis: Isis, Lady of Crocodiles?"). It is also intriguing to cite here that Sobek's mother was Neith, as noted by Richard H. Wilkinson (Wilkinson 157–159; 218–220); Gros de Beler notes that Neith was a female deity of the battle and she combined the traits of a woman and a man (Gros de Beler 64–65), which reminds us of Shakespeare's Cleopatra's desire to instruct her navy as a male general (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 3.7.49, 3.7.40–50, 3.7.1–75). Shakespeare's text connects between Cleopatra and the crocodile and the serpent (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.5.20–35, 2.7.20–30). In summation, Antony's consciousness connects Cleopatra with Egypt, and this perception connects Cleopatra with the dangerous creatures of the soil and the Nile. Lepidus thereby ponders over the organic generations, including the crocodile and the snake, associated with the sun and the Nile's/Egypt's soil (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.7.20–30).

Osiris and Antony

Antony's phallic identity and masculine prowess are influenced by Cleopatra. Lynne M. Simpson observes that Antony is perceived as a being of fertility and aquatics following his death, in the description given by Cleopatra to Dolabella (Simpson 69, 65–79; see Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 5.2.80–90). Antony is aware of his failing maleness, as he resolves to resist Cleopatra's control over him (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.2.120–125), yet the slime, greenery, exotic presence and impulse of life around the Nile draw him (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.7.16–30; for the information on Osiris's connection with fertility, see Wilkinson 118–123). The Egyptian ecosystem, in terms of temperature and moisture, affects Antony (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.3.60–76). Cleopatra also constitutes herself as a being of the waters and associates herself with the river's life forms. She seems to derive pleasure in being called the "serpent of the Old Nile" (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.5.20–35). The organic associations find expression through both the protagonists, implying that the equations between Osiris and Antony, and between Isis and Cleopatra, need to be interpreted in connection with the roles of Isis and Osiris in fertility (Hart 79–83, 114–124, 151–152). It is noteworthy also that Osiris and Isis were offsprings of Geb (the earth god whose body features moist soil, deserts, and mountains) and Nut (the goddess of the sky, whose body features stars, waters, and offers rain) (Wilkinson 78–79, 105–106, 160–163). Shakespeare also recontextualizes Antony as Geb and Cleopatra as Nut: just as Antony feels drawn to the "earth" and "clay" (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.5.20–35) associated with Geb, similarly Cleopatra wishes to ascend as "fire and air" (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 5.5.275–295), resembling Nut, from whose body rain and lightning descend. Symbolically, moisture and earth bind the protagonists together.

Gender-performance, which is significant in the mythic relationship between Isis and Osiris, is also a crucial feature of the relationship between Cleopatra and Antony. Shakespeare's ancient Romans, adhering to strict gender roles, associate masculinity with swords, which leads them to interpret Cleopatra's dalliance with the "swords" of both Julius Caesar and Antony as threats to Roman strength (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.2.235–245, 2.5.15–25). The Romans are wary of Cleopatra's control over the male bodies and men's virility; as evident in Agrippa's words, Cleopatra bears child after Julius Caesar "plough[s] her" (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.2.235–245). Antony's "sword Philippan" is possessed by Cleopatra (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.5.15–25). Simpson notes that Osiris's reconfiguration as the ruler of the Underworld and his acquirement of everlasting existence were both preceded by the substitution of his torn phallus by the "symbolic phallus" by Isis (Simpson 69, 65–79). If applied in the context of a Shakespearean play, Cleopatra's obsession with the swords/phalluses of both Julius Caesar and Antony also implies Isis's experimentation with a substituted phallus (Simpson 69, 65–79; see Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.2.235–245, 2.5.15–25). Mary Thomas Crane observes that, on the one hand, the "environment" of the play remains under the control of a Roman perception of the world based in "a Cartesian mind-body split"; on the other hand, the "environment" seems to have a profound impact on the Egyptians' thought processes (Crane 7, 1–17). Shakespeare thus makes Cleopatra resemble the fertile Nile Valley in a manner which fuses sharpness with tenderness, assertion with fruition, the human-manufactured objects with the organically existing/growing forms of Nature.

A comparison can be drawn between Antony's gradual decline and Osiris's suffering. Cleopatra refers to Antony's demise as a profound absence "[b]eneath the visiting moon" (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 4.15.65–70; see also Ray, "William Shakespeare's *Antony*

and Cleopatra” 00:55:18–00:58:12, slide no. 22). In the ancient Egyptian context, Shakespeare’s imagery is compelling as the ancient Egyptians drew an analogy between Osiris’s rejuvenation and the transition towards the full moon (for the link between Osiris and the moon, see Andrews 145–146, 102). This link illustrates how Cleopatra conceptualises her loss of Antony in a way similar to Isis’s loss of Osiris. When Cleopatra remembers Antony during her conversation with Dolabella, she describes Antony as an aquatic being, connected with the “realms and islands” (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 5.2.70–100), resembling Osiris, who was linked with the river and the vegetation (Oestigaard 86–88, 72–99). Seen from the ancient Egyptian point of view, if Cleopatra is linked with Isis, and by extension, with the sun as explored earlier, then Antony is linked with Osiris, and in extension, with the moon.

Shakespeare’s association of Antony with Osiris also underscores the gendered division and difference in human perceptions towards the “ecosystem” throughout the play. Crane notes that the ancient Roman minds established a connection between power, authority, and geography, while the ancient Egyptians were aware of “the natural cycles” that affect agriculture, climate, and flooding in the Nile Valley (Crane 9, 1–17). In ancient Egyptian mythology concerning Osiris, the putrefaction and restoration were important factors in embalmment (Oestigaard 80, 72–99). Oestigaard notes that the Nile connoted death (implying that the putrefying dead body of Osiris releases the waters of the “inundation”) and life (implying that the potential source of “life-juices” is contained in the waters) (Oestigaard 80, 72–99). Isis’s mourning for Osiris, which causes the yearly Inundation of the Nile, influences the land and its inhabitants in a fruitful manner (Oestigaard 86–88, 72–99). The “Inundation” represents the relationship between Isis and Osiris, communicated through the force and rhythm of water (Viaud 16–19; see also Oestigaard 86–88, 72–99); similarly, the passion between Antony and Cleopatra is like turbulent

waters. For example, Shakespeare, through Philo, describes Antony's attachment to Cleopatra as a "dotage" which "O'erflows the measure" (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.1.1–5), reminiscent of the Nile's flooding.

Shakespeare's Antony, with his penchant for liquid intoxication, is paralleled with Osiris, imbibing himself with "Egypt," the combined essence of Cleopatra, the Nile River, and the verdure of the nation (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.1.30–40, 2.7.16–25). Cleopatra's travel upon the Cydnus to meet Antony (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.2.200–230), her suggestion of naval fight (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 3.7.25–66, 3.7.15–66), and her vision of Antony floating on the waters before her demise (accounted in her conversation with Dolabella) (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 5.2.75–91) thereby fill the play with transmutation and liquid essence. Gillian M. E. Alban notes that through their mutual dalliance, both Cleopatra and Antony weave the Nile, the serpent, and Egypt in a network of aquatics, earth, venom, and mystery (Alban 96, 93–99; Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.5.20–35, 5.2.240–320). Cleopatra offers the rich "biodiversity" of Egypt and the nation's fertility to Antony; Antony absorbs the liquid warmth and pleasure through a gradual immersion of his masculine being (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.1.25–45, 1.3.60–76, 2.7.15–25). Edward J. Geisweidt argues that Antony's delving into liquid forms/states *endangers* his Roman identity, gendered fixities, and solidified control of his bodily self, even as liquid forms/states *engender* fecundity in Egypt (Geisweidt 94, 89–103). Antony, during his stays in Egypt, acquires lunar and aquatic qualities in Egyptian terms, becoming a figure like Osiris.

Just as Enobarbus, while conversing with Agrippa, describes Cleopatra on her barge as a spectacle amidst her subjects (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 2.2.200–255), similarly, Cleopatra, while conversing with Dolabella, paints Antony as a person of magnitude whose

person pervades the sky and “the ocean” (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 5.2.70–100). Wine and/or water is mentioned in the speeches by Cleopatra and Antony; the ancient Egyptians established connections between wine, Isis and Osiris. By referring to grapes, Shakespeare establishes a connection between Osiris and Antony (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 5.2.75–95, 5.2.279–315). Mark G. Boyer notes that the generation of wine follows the “crush[ing]” of grapes; this is symbolically analogical with Osiris’s “resurrection” after his assassination (Boyer 192). While depicting Cleopatra’s demise, Shakespeare poignantly makes Cleopatra remember the sweetness of grapes; this reminds the readers of Isis’s longing for Osiris (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 5.2.280–285).

Shakespeare’s play mentions that figs are brought to Cleopatra, contained in a basket, concealing an asp (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 5.2.230–325; see Ray, “Cleopatra VII Philopator’s Final Moments” 126–137). Shakespeare does not specify the type of fig. However, his text refers to the bringer of the serpent as “a rural fellow” (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 5.2.230–240) and “[a] simple countryman” (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 5.2.330–340) from which the readers may speculate that the figs could have been the “sycamore figs” found in the Egyptian desert (Varner 38; see also Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.5.19–35). The sycamore trees, as noted by Charlotte Booth, were important for the goddesses like Nut, Isis, and Hathor; Isis or Hathor would “incarnat[e]” themselves as the “Lady of the Sycamore” (Booth 38–39). The fig was also an ideal refreshment at the threshold of the living world beyond which the Afterlife exists, and the “etern[al]” survival of the dead was “ensure[d]” by water as well as figs from the sycamore trees (Booth 38–39).

In Egyptian iconography, the serpentine coil circles the solar disk of Ra and the “uraeus” may personify the “Eye of Ra” (an epithet for Hathor and/or Isis), which protects both the sun

god (in the Divine plane) (Writer/Composer Unknown, "Hymn VIII" 115–127; Žabkar 115–127) and the Pharaohs (in the terrestrial plane) by releasing fire (Pinch 128–131,184; Viaud 43). Through Cleopatra's demise, Shakespeare links the serpent (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 5.2.279–320) with Isis, and we have discussed Isis's connection with the sun earlier (see Ray, "Cleopatra VII Philopator's Final Moments" 126–137). Isis's maternal instincts nourish with tender warmth, and her protectiveness emits potent energy. Earlier in the play, Cleopatra cherishes her feelings for Antony, reflecting on the "serpent of the old Nile" epithet attached to her by Antony (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 1.5.19–35). During Cleopatra's suicide, she connects with the asp in a strange maternal instinct, which concretises her image as an Egyptian Queen, lover and mother (Shakespeare, *Antony and Cleopatra* 5.2.279–320).

Conclusion

References to "mythopoeic" information in Shakespeare's play help the readers explore ancient Egyptian icons, symbols, and metaphors present in the text, and provide interpretations different from conventional readings of the play. As Maria Valentini notes, the blend of Cleopatra's femininity and Antony's masculinity, which leads to "effeminacy," is seen as a rupture in the Roman militant gender-construct (Valentini 94, 87–102; see also Ray, "William Shakespeare's *Antony and Cleopatra*" 00:20:34–00:23:19, slide no. 8). The courtship and conjugal ties between Isis and Osiris shaped the landscape around the Nile; the life forms mentioned in the play also shape the elements in Cleopatra's character which itself along with the surroundings profoundly influence Antony. Their gendered performances also elevate them ambivalently in the eyes of the ancient Romans and the ancient Egyptians. Shakespeare's language demonstrates that the collective identities of the societies shape the native individuals.

Sajid Hussain, Barirah Nazir, Raheel Rehman Khan, and Abdul Rashid observe that the “cultural values” of the East influence Cleopatra and the “cultural values” of the West influence Antony (Hussain, Nazir, Khan, and Rashid 36, 32–37).

The contrasts in temperaments between Antony and Cleopatra are also products of the respective “ecosystems” of Rome and Egypt; however, the ancient Romans assert their control over Nature while Nature profoundly influence the characters and the temperaments of the ancient Egyptians. The ancient Egyptian responses to the “ecosystem” thereby feature variety in cognition and perception. Hussain, Nazir, Khan, and Rashid note that Cleopatra goes through an elemental transformation, towards airy as well as a flaming identity, considered masculine, elevating herself from the aquatic and the “rain[y]” features seen as feminine (Hussain, Nazir, Khan, and Rashid 35, 32–37). The iconographic representations in art elevated Cleopatra from an earthly woman to the position of Isis, the popular goddess, in the eye of the ancient Egyptians. Antony feels a connection with the Egyptian climate and Egyptian “biodiversity”; he therefore becomes an Osiris-figure. The information from Egyptologists helps us highlight the subtle but insightful references pertaining to the Isis-Osiris relationship, which may be of profound interest for the Egyptologists, Shakespeare scholars, and readers alike.

Endnotes

¹ The editor of the text of William Shakespeare’s *Antony and Cleopatra* used for discussion in this article is John Wilders; parenthetical citations in this article refer to Shakespeare’s text edited by Wilders. See the full citation in the “Works cited” list.

² The historical “Cleopatra VII Thea Philopator” and Shakespeare’s Cleopatra are different figures; for distinction, the names “Cleopatra VII” and “Cleopatra” are used to refer to the Ptolemaic Queen and the Queen-protagonist in Shakespeare’s play, respectively.

³ “Cleopatra VII Philopator’s Final Moments” is the shortened form of the title “Cleopatra VII Philopator’s Final Moments: Depictions in Five Paintings” of an article by Anirban Ray. See the

full citation in the "Works cited" list. The shortened form of the title is given in the in-text citations.

⁴ In the in-text citations referring to Shakespeare's *Antony and Cleopatra*, act numbers, scene numbers, and line numbers are mentioned.

⁵ "Teaching English Literary Texts with Approaches to Visual Arts" is the shortened form of the title "Teaching English Literary Texts with Approaches to Visual Arts: Three Case Studies" of an article by Anirban Ray. See the full citation in the "Works cited" list. The shortened form of the title is given in the in-text citations.

⁶ See the online lecture titled "William Shakespeare's *Antony and Cleopatra*: Interpreting the Protagonists: A Discussion" by Anirban Ray; for the discussion on the barge, listen to the section timed 00:49:29–00:50:55, 00:00:00–01:27:24 in this lecture, and see slide no. 19. The span of the entire file is approximately 00:00:00–01:27:24. Anirban Ray has developed this article from the online lecture (bilingual, with significant discussion in Bengali) given by him to the students of the Department of English, Basirhat College, Basirhat, West Bengal, India, on 18 Dec. 2021. The shortened title of the lecture is "William Shakespeare's *Antony and Cleopatra*"; the shortened form of the title is given in the in-text citations. For full citation of the lecture, see the "Works cited" list. See also Ray, "Teaching English Literary Texts," 20–22, 25–27.

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